

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES AND CONDITIONS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the pedagogical possibilities and conditions for improving the methodological training of primary school teachers based on the International Assessment Program. The importance of increasing the professionalism of teachers and introducing methodological approaches that meet the requirements of modern education is emphasized. The article considers international assessment criteria, the processes of updating teachers' knowledge and skills, as well as the importance of providing methodological assistance in educational institutions. Information is provided about trainings, seminars and practical exercises designed to improve the methodological training of teachers. It also emphasizes the need to create the necessary conditions to ensure the active participation of students in the educational process. The article concludes with recommendations to contribute to pedagogical progress.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, methodology, activity, student, teacher, modern, practical exercise, seminar, training.*

Introduction. In the world, effective technologies for improving the methodological preparation of teachers for teaching based on the international assessment program PIRLS - (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) are being implemented in the educational process. Training pedagogical personnel in accordance with the requirements of the time. Extensive work is being carried out to develop mechanisms for improving the professional and methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the International Assessment Programs (PIRLS), create multimedia electronic resources based on international assessment programs, and assess the quality of education.

Along with such work, work is being carried out to "improve the process and tools for assessing the quality of education, implement mechanisms that allow determining the achieved results", assess the level of knowledge of students based on international standards, and implement trends in improving the quality of teaching reading literacy subjects.

In higher education institutions around the world, scientific research is being conducted on ensuring the quality of teachers' methodological training for teaching based on the international assessment program PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study), modeling and designing the educational process, improving teachers' methodological training based on the international assessment program PIRLS, and international assessment programs for assessing student literacy (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS).

In this regard, scientific research on improving the professional and methodological training of future primary school teachers based on the International Program for the Evaluation

of Teachers (PIRLS) and conducting professional training based on international qualification requirements, raising the quality of education to an international level, conducting diagnostics of the level of development of skills for solving international research tasks (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS), establishing modular education, activating social communication, and determining the professionalism of primary school teachers is of particular importance.

Literature review. Research on the issues of improving the professional and methodological training of future primary school teachers based on international assessment programs (PIRLS) was conducted by B.S.Abdullaeva, A.A.Abduqodirov, N.A.Muslimov, A.A.Kholikov.

Research on the issues of improving the professional and methodological training of primary school teachers was conducted by U.A.Masharipova, N.Sh.Ruzikulova, M.I.Toshpo'latova, A.A.Urazimbetova, M.Akhmedov, B.L.Akhmedova, N.U.Bikbayeva, Z.Dadanov, R.A.Mavlonova, K.T.Olimov, M.A.Zaynitdinova, M.Jumayev, R.Adizov.

In the CIS countries, this topic was reflected in the research of such scientists as Sh. Kurmanalina, N. Istomina, N. V. Ammosova, Z. I. Yansufina, A. B. Abramov, F. S. Avdeev, V. V. Afanasev, S. M. Batashova, M. A. Bantova, A. M. Berestovsky, G. Yu. Burakova, D. A. Vlasov, H. A. Demchenkova, I. V. Drobisheva, Z. M. Kondrashova, O. A. Lapina, G. A. Medyanik, O. Tarasova, T. Havenson, A. Zakharov, A. Kseniya, M. Karnoy, P. Loyalka, V. Schmidt, I. A. Baygusheva, D. U. Baisalov, T. I. Bacharova.

We can see that foreign scholars I.V.S.Mullis, M.O.Martin, P.Goh, D.L.Kelly, B.Fishbein, Akiba, M., LeTendre, G.K., & Scribner, J.P, Y.Andyers, H.G.Rossbach, S.Weinyert, S.Ebyert, S.Kugyer, S.Lehrl, and J. Von Maurice, J.E.Gustafsson, K.Y.Hansen, M.Rosén Blank, R.K., & de las Alas, Wardat Yousef, Belbase Shashidhar, Tairab Hassan, Pavneet Kaur Bharaj have put forward their ideas about the international assessment system and its scope and comparative analysis across countries.

Research methodology. This study aims to identify pedagogical opportunities and conditions for improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the international assessment program. The research used observation, interview, pedagogical experience and analysis methods. At the initial stage, the level of logical thinking of future teachers was measured through diagnostic tests. At the next stage, a system of exercises for students based on the PIRLS international assessment program was developed and used in the experimental group. The results obtained were compared with the indicators of the control group, and the positive impact of the PIRLS international assessment program on the development of methodological preparation of future primary school teachers was identified. At the end of the study, all data were summarized based on statistical and qualitative analysis.

Analysis and results. In recent years, in our republic, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” (No. PF-5712) dated April 29, 2019, five initiatives have been implemented, including comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for the education of young people. A normative framework is being created for improving teaching methodologies, as well as for the gradual introduction of the principles of individualization in the educational process, as well as for the training, retraining and advanced training of professional personnel, the introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of public education, and participation in international research on assessing the quality of education.

This will expand the opportunities for future primary school teachers to improve their methodological preparation in the light of new pedagogical technologies and international assessment programs. PIRLS provides trends and international comparisons of fourth-grade students' reading achievement and students' competencies related to reading education goals and standards.

PIRLS assesses two main reading goals that account for much of the reading that young students do both in and out of school: literary experiences and acquiring and using information. In addition, PIRLS assesses four broad comprehension processes within each of the two reading goals: paying attention to and retrieving clearly expressed information, making direct inferences, interpreting and integrating ideas and information, and evaluating and critiquing content and text elements.

In addition to assessing reading, the PIRLS school, teacher, student, and home surveys collect extensive information about the contextual factors at home and school that are relevant to the teaching and learning of reading. This rich data includes information about how the education system is organized to facilitate learning; students' home environments and learning supports; school climate and resources; and how teaching is typically delivered in the classroom. PIRLS also provides an encyclopedia that contains information about each country's educational context for learning to read. National research coordinators play a key role in identifying the passages, developing questions and surveys, and developing the PIRLS encyclopedia. They also lead the assessment in their country; report on the results, and interpret the findings in a national context.

PIRLS Assessment Options. PIRLS evolves with each assessment cycle to stay current. For the first time, PIRLS 2021 will be delivered through a digital, web-based delivery system. The PIRLS Reading Assessment includes a variety of reading texts presented in an engaging and visually appealing format that encourages students to read and interact with the texts and answer comprehension questions.

PIRLS includes the PIRLS assessment of online reading, which began in 2016. PIRLS measures how well students read, interpret, and critique online information in an Internet-like environment. Guided by a teacher avatar, students navigate within and across web pages to answer questions, explain relationships, and interpret and integrate information. Web pages include visual information, including photos, charts, and maps, as well as navigation and dynamic features, such as animations, hyperlinks, and pop-ups. Taken as a single, continuous, digitally-based effort, PIRLS provides a state-of-the-art assessment of 21st-century reading skills. Countries administering PIRLS can take advantage of the advantages of computer-based assessments, including greater operational efficiencies in translation and translation checking, data entry, and scoring, without the need to print or mail. PIRLS is delivered as a web-based system via school or IEA web servers or via a USB drive connected locally to a personal computer running the Windows operating system.

As an alternative to PIRLS, countries can administer a paper-based version of PIRLS, which will be reported alongside PIRLS. PIRLS is suitable for a wide range of countries. PIRLS 2021 uses a cohort-based design. All countries administer the same reading passages and items, but the rate of distribution of the different test forms within a country is adjusted to the population. This innovative, flexible design improves the measurement of PIRLS reading across all levels of distribution for countries with different reading proficiency levels, while increasing student engagement.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, it can be said that the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching based on the international assessment program will be improved by teaching them to combine information from two or more sources, draw conclusions based on the information, and create a working integrative-didactic environment aimed at ensuring the effectiveness of cognitive-creative, process-integrative criteria.

The following recommendations have been developed to improve the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the International Assessment Programs (PIRLS):

1. Improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the International Assessment Programs (PIRLS).

2. Improving the professional and methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the International Assessment Programs (PIRLS), linking it with practice, and improving it based on the principles of educational and developmental education.

3. Improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching based on the PIRLS international assessment program.

4. Developing methodological recommendations based on providing non-traditional communicative methods and electronic didactic tools for teaching future primary school teachers based on the PIRLS international assessment program.

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